

Case Report

Endometrial Mesonephric-Like Adenocarcinoma: A Case Report of an Aggressive Rare Endometrial Cancer

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Keywords

• Mesonephric-like Adenocarcinoma; Uterus; Endometrium; Endometrial cancer; MLA

Abstract

Background: Endometrial mesonephric adenocarcinoma is a rare aggressive tumor of the female genital tract, which originates from mesonephric duct remnants. Its diagnosis is pathologically challenging, because it may exhibit a mixture of morphological patterns that complicates the differential diagnosis.

Case: A 56-year-old female para 2, gravida 2, presented with multiple episodes of vaginal bleeding. Treated with 52 mg levonorgestrel-releasing intrauterine system. Follow-up endometrial sampling every 6 months converted to normal, inactive endometrium at one year. After more than 4 years of amenorrhea, she presented with multiple episodes of vaginal bleeding again. A repeat endometrial biopsy showed atypical glandular proliferation, cannot exclude endometrioid adenocarcinoma. She underwent a total laparoscopic hysterectomy, bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy. The final pathology of the uterine specimen was reported as a mesonephric like adenocarcinoma, an unusual histological type of uterine neoplasia.

Conclusion: Mesonephric-like adenocarcinomas are considered high-grade carcinomas, even though they have a misleadingly low-grade morphology. Endometrial biopsy can be misleading such that it can delay diagnosis. This case demonstrates that reassuring endometrial sampling may not be sufficient to evaluate these unusual tumors and that progesterone therapy may not be sufficient to manage or prevent progression of these rare, high-grade tumors. Previous literature describes these tumors as having a high risk of recurrence and a high tendency for metastasis, especially to the lung and brain. A multidisciplinary team is necessary to optimize management. Unfortunately, treatment options are limited and the best therapeutic strategy is yet to be determined. Further research on the pathogenesis should help better understand this specific subset of endometrial cancer.

INTRODUCTION

Mesonephric carcinoma of the uterine corpus is a rare malignancy that is postulated to originate from the mesonephric remnant of the female reproductive tract [1]. The mesonephric duct, which parallels the paramesonephric duct during the embryonic stage, forms the male epididymis, vas deferens, seminal vesicles, partial prostate and urethra.

Due to the lack of androgens, the mesonephric duct degenerates in female embryos. The mesonephric remnant in females is typically located in the ovary, broad ligament and cervical sidewalls, although it may rarely be located in the vaginal wall or myometrium.

Due to the limited number of cases reported of mesonephric carcinoma occurring within the myometrium, there is limited information regarding the diagnosis and treatment of this malignancy.

It is still a matter of controversy whether these tumors are of mesonephric origin or represent Müllerian neoplasms closely mimicking mesonephric adenocarcinomas. They show morphological, immunohistochemical and molecular similarities to mesonephric adenocarcinomas (MA), that originate from true mesonephric remnants. Most importantly, Mesonephric-

like adenocarcinomas (MLA), are often misdiagnosed as other endometrial neoplasms, but have an aggressive clinical behavior and tend to metastasize early to the lungs [3-6].

CASE

A 56-year-old Columbian female gravida 2, para 2 with a Body Mass Index (BMI) of BMI 28 presented with multiple episodes of post-menopausal vaginal bleeding. An endometrial biopsy performed was reported as "small fragments of atypical cribriform glandular proliferation, cannot exclude endometrioid adenocarcinoma." A 52 mg levonorgestrel-releasing intrauterine system (IUS) had been in place over the previous 52 months due to an earlier biopsy report that originally showed evidence of endometrial hyperplasia without atypia at that time. She had not experienced any bleeding over that period of time. She underwent multiple endometrial biopsies following hormonal IUS insertion that were reported as inactive endometrium. Otherwise, the patient was asymptomatic, and medically healthy. She was a non-smoker and not taking any other medications.

Due to the persistent vaginal spotting and the non-reassuring endometrial biopsy report despite progesterone treatment, she underwent a total laparoscopic hysterectomy, bilater-

al salpingo-oophorectomies. Uterus, ovaries and fallopian tubes were grossly normal at the time of surgery. The final pathology of the uterine specimen showed an unusual histology type of uterine neoplasia, specifically “mesonephric like adenocarcinoma”, with 10 of 12 mm depth of myometrial invasion and diffuse lymphovascular invasion. Ovaries and tubes were negative for malignancy. Additional genetic testing of the tissue revealed intact nuclear expression of Lynch-type genetic mutations with variable P53 mutation present on immunohistochemistry. She recovered well post-operatively. Fortunately, a whole body CT scan did not reveal any metastatic lesions. These findings correspond to a FIGO stage II endometrial adenocarcinoma.

This case was reviewed by the GYN Oncology Multidisciplinary team, comprised of representation from Pathology, Radiation Oncology, Medical Oncology, and Gynecologic Oncology and the question of “best adjuvant treatment” was addressed.

All concurred that adjuvant radiotherapy would probably benefit this patient. However, even though there is no conclusive evidence in the medical literature to guide the use of adjuvant chemotherapy, it was decided that it would be reasonable to administer chemotherapy. Radical radiotherapy was planned first, followed by 6 cycles of Taxol/carboplatin.

HISTOPATHOLOGY

The specimen pathology was Mesonephric-like adenocarcinoma of the endometrium with 10 of 12 mm (85 %) of myometrial invasion and no serosal involvement. Adenomyosis was present in areas uninvolved with the carcinoma. There was extensive lower uterine segment and cervical stromal involvement extending into the anterior and posterior myometria with more than 5 foci of diffuse lymphovascular space invasion present. The tumour was not grossly identified and the primary tumour found in the lower uterine segment was determined by microscopic examination. Cervical stromal invasion was up to 85% of the total thickness with negative paracervical/parametrial margins.

The carcinoma was predominantly situated in the lower uterine segment and cervix and had variable morphology including infiltrative, angulated glands as well as cribriform nests, some with solid, central spindled cells, and calcifications. Some of the glands displayed nuclear clearing and the lumens contained eosinophilic material.

The carcinoma cells showed variable staining for: vimentin (positive in cribriform and negative in single glands areas); estrogen receptors (ER) (patchy in area of single glands); progesterone receptors (PR)(focal patchy in area of single glands); GATA3 (patchy in cribriform and single glands areas), CD10 (some apical staining); calretinin (patchy in cribriform area); and p16 (very focal and weak). Cells were negative for monoclonal Carcino-Embryonic Antigen (CEA) and TTF-1. p53 was variable and patchy, consistent with wild-type immunophenotype.

There was no loss of nuclear expression of mismatch repair proteins. These findings indicate that this carcinoma is very unlikely to be associated with Lynch syndrome (LS). While tumours in patients with LS typically show abnormal mismatch repair

protein expression, the immunohistochemical findings cannot entirely exclude the possibility of LS.

DISCUSSION

Epidemiology

Mesonephric-like adenocarcinomas are rare neoplasms with a reported incidence of 1% of all endometrial carcinomas [5,6]. In the literature, 115 uterine and 39 ovarian cases have been reported (14). Of these, 16 mesonephric-like adenocarcinomas had associated findings of Müllerian as opposed to Non-Müllerian origin such as adenomyosis [7,8], endometriosis [7,9], atypical hyperplasia of the endometrium (or EIN) [10], serous cystadenoma [9], mixed serous and mucinous cystadenoma [9], serous borderline tumor [9], borderline endometrioid adenofibroma [9], low-grade endometrioid endometrial carcinoma [11], low-grade serous ovarian carcinoma [9]. All age groups can be affected, ranging from 26 to 91 years with a mean of 59 years and a median of 61 years.

Pathogenesis

The cell lineage of origin is still a matter of debate. With the morphology reminiscent of classic mesonephric carcinoma and overlapping immunohistochemical features, it could be a type of mesonephric carcinoma with divergent Müllerian features. However, proteomic analysis of both MA and MLA are essentially identical [12]. On the other hand, uterine tumors tend to originate from the endometrium with secondary involvement of the myometrium and they are not associated with mesonephric remnants. Cases where the MLA is associated with other Müllerian lesions support the evidence of a Müllerian lesion that differentiated along mesonephric lines.

Prognosis

Mesonephric-like adenocarcinomas have aggressive biological behavior with more than half of the published cases presented at an advanced stage (FIGO \geq II) on diagnosis. They are associated with a considerable risk of recurrent disease with a tendency to metastasize to the lungs [3,4,5,6,9]. Not only advanced stage but also lower stage disease can frequently metastasize [6,11,15,16]. This was confirmed by Pors et al., who calculated that the stage at diagnosis was not significant for progression-free survival. They reported a 5-year overall survival of 71 to 72% for mesonephric adenocarcinomas of the uterine body and ovary [10]. Six characteristics were significantly associated with the development of metastasis, including large tumor size (>4 cm), ill-defined tumor border, advanced FIGO stages (III to IV), presence of coagulative tumor cell necrosis, high mitotic activity (>10/10 high-power fields), and presence of lymphovascular invasion. High mitotic activities and lymphovascular invasion were found to be independent factors [6]. Compared with other endometrial adenocarcinomas, MLAs have better overall survival than malignant mixed Müllerian tumors, equal overall survival to serous and grade 3 endometrioid carcinoma, and worse overall survival than grade 1–2 endometrioid carcinomas [10]. Endometrial carcinomas have a tendency for lymphovascular metastasis to pelvic lymph nodes followed by retroperitoneal lymph nodes. Distant metastases in endometrial carcinoma are rare with a reported incidence of 3.1% (all tumor

types) [17], although the lungs are the most common site (1.5%).

Treatment

In the literature, all cases were staged and treated with a total hysterectomy and bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy. Pelvic lymph node dissection was often added, potentially also with para-aortic lymph node dissection. Adjuvant chemotherapy, mainly carboplatin + paclitaxel, was reserved for advanced stage disease but also in one case of FIGO stage IA and two cases of FIGO stage IB [6,8,14]. Radiation therapy was given solo in early cases with the addition of chemotherapy in advanced cases. Two reported cases were treated with hormone therapy [3,11,14]. One case was initially diagnosed as a low-grade EEC, was treated with progesterone therapy, with the concurrent mesonephric-like adenocarcinoma component only retrospectively recognized 6 years later when the MLA became more apparent [11]. The other case was also diagnosed as EEC, grade 1–2, the type of hormone therapy was not specified. This tumor recurred with distant metastasis to the liver after 17 months [3,14].

The optimal regimen and the efficacy of (neo) adjuvant radiation and or chemotherapy remains largely unknown. So far, no tumor-specific treatment options have been elucidated for mesonephric-like adenocarcinomas [14].

CONCLUSIONS

Mesonephric-like adenocarcinomas are considered high-grade carcinomas, even though they have a misleadingly low-grade morphology. Endometrial biopsy can be misleading and could delay diagnosis and treatment. The tumors have a high risk of recurrence and a high tendency for lung metastasis. The impact of hormonal therapy on the behaviour of this tumour is unclear but could contribute to delayed diagnosis. A multidisciplinary team is recommended to approach management although optimal treatment is not clear and the best therapeutic strategy is yet to be determined. Further research into the pathogenesis should help better understand this specific subset of endometrial cancer and elucidate preferred treatment of this rare neoplasm.

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